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FACTORS AFFECTING YOUNG PEOPLE'S DECISIONS TO VISIT SPIRITUAL TOURISM DESTINATIONS: THE CASE OF LINH UNG PAGODA IN SON TRA, DANANG CITY, VIETNAM

Abstract. This paper aims to study the influence of factors on young people's decisions to visit Linh Ung Pagoda in Son Tra, Danang city, Vietnam. Research data were collected from 240 students currently studying at universities in Vietnam through a convenience sampling method. In the study, several research methods were used such as descriptive statistics, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), and multiple linear regression analysis. The results of the study show that two factors influenced young people's decisions to visit Linh Ung Pagoda in Son Tra, including (1) travel motivation and (2) the costs of the trip. Through research results, this paper has proposed some important recommendations to promote young people's choice to visit spiritual tourism destinations.

Keywords: Spiritual tourism, Visiting decision, Young people, Linh Ung pagoda, Son Tra, Danang city, Vietnam

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ФАКТОРЫ, ВЛИЯЮЩИЕ НА РЕШЕНИЕ МОЛОДЫХ ЛЮДЕЙ ПОСЕТИТЬ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ ДУХОВНОГО ТУРИЗМА (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ПАГОДЫ ЛИНЬ УНГ В СОН ЧА, ГОРОД ДАНАНГ, ВЬЕТНАМ)

Целью статьи является изучение влияния факторов на решение молодых людей посетить пагоду Линь Унг в Сон Ча, город Дананг, Вьетнам. Исследование основано на опросе 240 вьетнамских студентов, которые в настоящее время обучаются в университетах Вьетнама, с помощью метода репрезентативной выборки. Методы исследования – описательная статистика, исследовательский факторный анализ (EFA) и множественный линейный регрессионный анализ. В результате исследования были выделены 2 из 4 групп факторов, влияющих на решение молодых людей посетить пагоду Линь Унг в Сон Ча, в том числе (1) мотивация путешествия и (2) стоимость поездки. По результатам исследования в статье предложен ряд важных рекомендаций для мотивации молодёжи к посещению духовных туристических направлений.

Ключевые слова: *духовный туризм, решение о посещении, молодёжь, пагода Линь Унг, Сон Ча, город Дананг, Вьетнам*

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1. Introduction

Nowadays, this form of spiritual tourism is prevalent. Many people visit spiritual places to find peace and relaxation after tiring working days. Spiritual tourism destinations possess unique cultures and beliefs and extremely beautiful sightseeing and check-in places. Regarding spiritual tourism, many researchers in the world have discussed the issue of spiritual tourism from the perspective of religion [2]. According to Norman (2012), spiritual tourism as an individual phenomenon aims to explore life outside of oneself to balance body-mind-soul, achieve self-awareness to improve the spirit, and realize the purpose of life [15]. Spiritual tourism is defined as "a journey to find the purpose of life, and it is a lively exploration that goes beyond the self. It contributes to the balance of the body-mind-spirit, which may or may not have a relationship with religion" [3; 16]. Besides, Abdul Halim et al. (2021) also built a conceptual model of spiritual tourism including 7 themes: purpose of life, consciousness, transcendence, spiritual resource, self-determination, reflection-soul purification, and spiritual coping [3].

Spiritual tourism in the world in general and Vietnam in particular has become an increasingly popular trend. In recent years, Vietnam's tourism industry has grown strongly, spiritual tourism has contributed greatly and sustainably to that growth. Danang city is located in the geographical center of Vietnam, and it is the center of 3 world cultural heritages: Hue Imperial City, Hoi An Ancient Town, and My Son Sanctuary. Danang not only includes famous tourist destinations and modern amusement parks, but Danang tourism is also a gathering place for many spiritual tourist destinations with great spiritual significance. Danang has many famous spiritual places such as Ngu Hanh Son tourist area, Linh Ung Pagoda in Son Tra, Linh Ung Pagoda in Non Nuoc, Linh Ung Pagoda in Ba Na, Nam Son Pagoda, etc. Among them, Linh Ung Pagoda in Son Tra is one of the famous spiritual destinations and attracts a large number of domestic and international tourists because of its special architecture. This pagoda

has the tallest Quan The Am Buddha statue in Vietnam at 67 m.

According to Dr. Nguyen Anh Tuan – Director of the Institute of Tourism Development Research, the travel demand of young people is increasing. "Cultural-spiritual" tourism is identified as one of the trends attracting attention and becoming increasingly popular among the young Vietnamese community. However, up to now, no author has studied the factors that influence young people's decisions to visit spiritual tourism destinations. These influencing factors play an important role for travel companies to come up with strategies to attract young tourists to visit spiritual destinations. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to identify factors that influence young people's decisions to visit spiritual tourism destinations, in the case study at Linh Ung Pagoda in Son Tra, Danang city, Vietnam.

2. Hypotheses and research model

Travel motivation

According to Li et al. (2015), travel motivation is a set of different attributes that are why a person participates in a travel activity [14]. Many empirical studies have identified travel motivation as one of the important factors influencing the decision to choose a destination or the decision to visit a tourist destination (Um & Crompton, 1990; Kyriakaki et al., 2020; Solikhah & Andjarwati, 2021; Andjarwati et al., 2023). Research by Valeri (2023) has also demonstrated that travel motivation plays an important role in spiritual tourism consumption [19]. The research hypothesis is proposed as follows:

Hypothesis H₁: Travel motivation has a positive effect on young people's decisions to visit spiritual tourism destinations.

The destination attraction

Hu and Ritchie (1993) defined destination attractiveness as including all the possibilities that a destination brings satisfaction and benefits to tourists [9]. Attractiveness is an important factor for tourists [7]. Brian & Kurniawan's research on tourists' decision factors to visit spiritual tourism destinations: Case of St. Mary Grotto Kerep Ambarawa, shows that destination attractiveness

is an important factor influencing the decision to visit spiritual tourism destinations [5]. Therefore, the research hypothesis is proposed as follows:

Hypothesis H₂: The destination attraction has a positive effect on young people's decisions to visit spiritual tourism destinations.

Sources of information about the destination

Tourists are motivated to visit a destination through information received from a provider tailored to their needs and desires [8]. Many studies have confirmed the importance of destination information sources in influencing the decision to visit a tourist destination such as Fodness & Murray (1997); Jacobsen & Munar (2012); and Azim Ahmed & Ramadan Abdul Kadir (2013). Young people often do not have much travel experience, so they need to know more information about the destination to make decisions to visit spiritual tourism destinations. Therefore, the research hypothesis is proposed as follows:

Hypothesis H₃: Destination information sources have a positive effect on young people's decisions to visit spiritual tourism destinations.

Costs of the trip

Cost/price is one of the factors affecting the competitiveness of a destination as well as tourists' decisions to choose to visit a destination. These costs include the cost of traveling to the destination, the cost of using products/services at the destination, and the cost of leaving the destination. Research by Brian & Kurniawan shows that price influences a tourist's decision to visit a spiritual tourism destination [5]. Reality shows that the lower the cost of the trip, the higher the decision to visit the tourist destination and vice versa. Therefore, the research hypothesis is proposed as follows:

Hypothesis H₄: Costs of the trip have a negative effect on young people's decisions to visit spiritual tourism destinations.

3. Research methods

Qualitative research methods were used to explore, adjust, and supplement scale components. We have compiled and analyzed scientific

articles related to satisfaction with spiritual tourism, criteria for choosing spiritual tourism destinations, and tourists' deciding factors to visit spiritual tourism destinations. The collection of previous studies to have a solid theoretical basis for building research hypotheses and models.

Figure 1 – Proposed research model

Besides, we have also combined quantitative research methods to test the research model and research hypotheses using multiple linear regression analysis through the following steps:

1) Conduct research data collection using survey questionnaires via Google Forms. The questionnaire used the Likert scale (5 levels) to measure young people's decision factors to visit spiritual tourism destinations through 4 groups of factors: travel motivation, destination attraction, sources of information about the destination, and costs of the trip. According to Hair et al. [10], the minimum expected sample for performing exploratory factor analysis (EFA) needs to be 5 times the total number of observed variables. Therefore, the minimum sample size of this study was 125, corresponding to the 25 variables identified. To ensure the sample size condition, We surveyed 250 students currently studying at universities in Vietnam.

2) Collected information was processed by SPSS 22.0 software and analyzed data: Descriptive statistics of analyzed samples; analyze Cronbach's Alpha coefficient and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to evaluate the reliability of the scale, thereby eliminating observed variables that

do not meet reliability; regression analysis to identify factors that influence the decisions to visit spiritual tourism destinations.

4. Research results

4.1. Descriptive statistics

The study received 250 surveys from students, of which 240 were valid surveys. This study eliminated invalid surveys such as the surveyor was not a student, the surveyor had never been to visit Linh Ung Pagoda in Son Tra, Danang city. The number of valid votes was processed using SPSS 22.0 software. Characteristics of the study sample are shown in Table 1 as follows:

Table 1 – Characteristics of research sample

Characteristics		Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	80	33.3
	Female	160	63.7
Age	Below 20	112	46.7
	21–25	128	53.3
Are you currently a student?	Yes	240	100.0
	No	0	0
What is your religion?	Non-religion	144	60
	Buddhism	96	40
Who have you ever visited Linh Ung Pagoda in Son Tra with?	Alone	16	6.7
	Family	88	36.7
	Friends, colleagues, etc.	136	56.7

The survey results show that the proportion of females (63.7%) was higher than males (33.3%) among the 240 respondents surveyed. This study aims at young tourists so we limited our sample

to students between 18 and 35 years old who are currently studying at universities in Vietnam. From the 240 students that filled out the survey, most of the respondents were 21-25 years of age (53.3%), followed by those who were under 20 years of age (46.7%). Regarding the religion of the respondents, 60% of students do not follow any religion and the remaining 40% of their religion is Buddhism. The majority of students visited Linh Ung Pagoda with friends and colleagues (56.7%), followed by those who visited this destination with their families (36.7%) or alone (6.7%).

4.2. Test-retest reliability and exploratory factor analysis of the scale

Based on the proposed research model, we developed a survey questionnaire and surveyed students studying at universities in Vietnam and those who have visited Linh Ung Pagoda in Son Tra, Danang. In the model, we built a dependent variable and 4 independent variables with 25 observations. The results of testing the reliability of the scale are shown in Table 2.

The results from Table 2 show that the lowest Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of the scales was 0.798 and the corrected item-total correlation coefficient of the smallest representative variable was 0.507. The corrected item-total correlation coefficients of the observed variables were greater than 0.3 and Cronbach's Alpha coefficients were greater than 0.6 [10]. Therefore, all 25 observed variables were accepted and they will be used in exploratory factor analysis.

Table 2 – Cronbach's alpha results

Measurement variables	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Independent variables				
1. Travel motivation (MO): $\alpha = 0.895$				
MO1	15.400	10.015	0.694	0.883
MO2	15.167	9.244	0.814	0.855
MO4	15.267	9.301	0.841	0.849
MO5	15.200	10.336	0.691	0.883
MO6	15.233	10.556	0.672	0.887
2. The destination attraction (AT): $\alpha = 0.928$				
AT1	16.000	9.105	0.576	0.956
AT2	16.300	7.843	0.924	0.888
AT3	15.967	7.932	0.899	0.893

Measurement variables	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
AT4	15.833	8.842	0.838	0.909
AT5	16.433	7.878	0.854	0.902
3. Sources of information about the destination (INF): $\alpha = 0.873$				
INF1	18.800	9.131	0.728	0.844
INF2	19.367	8.668	0.648	0.858
INF3	19.167	9.646	0.619	0.861
INF4	18.567	9.820	0.507	0.879
INF5	18.967	8.468	0.779	0.833
INF6	19.133	8.150	0.794	0.830
4. Costs of the trip (CT): $\alpha = 0.881$				
CT1	7.567	2.857	0.727	0.872
CT2	7.667	2.901	0.810	0.798
CT3	7.700	2.822	0.776	0.826
Dependent variable				
Decide to visit Linh Ung pagoda (DC): $\alpha = 0.902$				
DC1	11.800	8.261	0.655	0.922
DC2	11.433	8.347	0.836	0.857
DC3	11.567	7.410	0.829	0.856
DC4	11.600	8.141	0.832	0.856

Table 3 – Results of exploratory factor analysis for independent variables

Observed variables	Factors			
	1	2	3	4
AT3	.947			
AT2	.934			
AT4	.901			
AT5	.895			
AT1	.712			
INF5		.876		
INF2		.839		
INF6		.833		
INF1		.741		
INF3		.686		
INF4		.504		
MO4			.874	
MO2			.825	
MO5			.769	
MO1			.722	
MO6			.656	
CT2				.893
CT1				.809
CT3				.799
Coefficient KMO	0.537			
Extracted variance (%)	75.643			
Sig. in Bartlett's Test	0.000			

Table 4 – Results of exploratory factor analysis for the dependent variable

Observed variables	Factor
DC1	0.895
DC2	0.923
DC3	0.908
DC4	0.921

Some important criteria in exploratory factor analysis include: $0.5 < KMO$ (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) < 1 [3], Factor loading must be greater than 0.5 and Total variance extracted must be greater than 60%. The results of the first EFA analysis show that the KMO coefficient was $0.516 > 0.5$ and the results of Bartlett's test with significance level $Sig = 0.000 < 0.05$, so the observed variables in the population were correlated together, this proves that the data used for factor analysis are completely appropriate. However, the variable AT6 was isolated in the 5th factor, so we removed the variable AT6 from the scale.

In the second EFA analysis, variable MO3 loaded on two factors 1 and 4 with loading factors of 0.514 and 0.510, respectively. According to Matt C. Howard (2015), if an observed variable loads on two factors but the difference in the loading factor is less than 0.2, the observed variable

should be considered for removal. Therefore, we also removed the variable MO3 from the scale. The third EFA analysis from 19 observed variables had 4 factors extracted with KMO coefficient was 0.537 and Sig = 0.00 at Eigenvalues was 1.251 with a total variance extracted was 75.643%. All coefficients ensure conditions for subsequent analysis.

4.3. Regression analysis

From the regression analysis results in Table 5, the adjusted R² coefficient of the regression model was 0.766. This indicates that 4 independent variables including travel motivation, the destination attraction, information sources about the destination, and costs of the trip contributed to explaining 76.6% of the decision to visit Linh Ung Pagoda for young people. The Sig (F test) = 0.000 < 0.05, so the regression model is appropriate. The variables included in the model did not have multicollinearity when the VIF coefficient was less than 2, and there was also no correlation when the coefficient d of the Durbin – Watson test had a value of 1.5 < 2.016 < 2.5.

Table 5 – Results of regression analysis

Model	Standard. Coeff. Beta	Sig.	VIF	Decision
(Constant)		0.041		
Travel motivation	0.922	0.000	1.970	Accepted
The destination attraction	0.047	0.158	1.122	Rejected
Source of information about the destination	0.026	0.461	1.286	Rejected
Costs of the trip	- 0.088	0.035	1.772	Accepted
R Square	0.770			
R Square Adjusted	0.766			
Sig. (F-Test)	0.000			
Durbin – Watson	2.016			

However, among the 4 variables, only 2 variables had a statistical significance level of less than 0.05 (travel motivation and costs of the trip). Thus, it can be concluded that both MO and CT variables have an impact on young people's decisions to visit Linh Ung Pagoda in Son Tra, Danang city. In particular, the MO variable had a positive impact and the CT variable had a negative impact

on the decision to visit Linh Ung Pagoda. The remaining two variables AT (Sig. = 0.158 > 0.05) and INF (Sig. = 0.461 > 0.05) did not influence young people's decision to visit. Therefore, the study rejected these two observed variables. From the results of the regression analysis, we set up a standardized regression equation as follows:

$$DC = 0.922 \times MO - 0.088 \times CT$$

Through the data shown in the regression equation, under the condition that the remaining independent variables were unchanged and when evaluating the variable "travel motivation" (MO) increased by one unit, lead to a change of the variable "decide to visit Linh Ung pagoda" increased by 0.922 units; and if the variable of "costs of the trip" (CT) increased by one unit, the decide to visit Linh Ung pagoda decreased by 0.088 units. Through the standardized Beta coefficients, we can recognize the importance of factors influencing young people's decisions to visit Linh Ung Pagoda in Son Tra, Danang. In particular, "travel motivation" had the most influence (0.922), followed by "costs of the trip" (0.088).

5. Discussion and conclusions

This study aims to identify the factors that are influencing young people's decisions to visit spiritual tourism destinations. The main findings indicated that in general, travel motivation was the most influential factor in young people's decisions to visit Linh Ung Pagoda in Son Tra, Danang city, followed by the factor "costs of the trip".

According to the research results, to attract young people to decide to visit spiritual tourism destinations, we proposed some recommendations as follows:

1) Develop appropriate travel expense policies. Local tourism management agencies need to coordinate with tourism business units to develop policies on tourism costs at spiritual tourism destinations to suit young tourists.

2) Exploiting young people's motivation to visit spiritual tourism destinations. Spiritual destinations need to research specifically on the characteristics of this segment. Grasp the psychology of young tourists well to come up with appropriate attraction policies.

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